

QUIZ**LAST NAME: MUSIKOYO****FIRST NAME: MUNOKO****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX (6)****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. What is the recommended style guide for writers according to Euclid University? (Specifically, for Euclid University students)**
 - MLA handbook rules of writing.
 - Chicago rules (Turabian).¹**
 - Associated Press (AP) stylebook.
 - The Elements of style.
- 2. Writers are advised to avoid plagiarism. What is plagiarism?**
 - Using a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, 2nd ed.* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 24.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 5.

- Using the exact words from a source of information with quotation marks or indentation.
 - Using the ideas of another writer with proper citation.
 - All the above are considered as forms of plagiarism.
3. **According to Turabian guidelines, which of the following elements may be included in the front matter of your thesis?**
- Abstract, preface, literature review, epigraph.
 - Bibliography, endnotes, reference list, list of figures.
 - Submission page, title page, copyright page, table of contents.**³
 - Appendices, illustrations, glossary, footnotes.
4. **What are the three common conceptual questions that an experienced researcher should ask?**
- I am working on the topic X, so I can find good evidence to support my answer Y, and disapprove my answer Z.
 - I am working on the topic X, because I want to find out Y, so that I can help others understand Z.**⁴
 - I am working on the topic X, because I want to change the world with Y, and be known for Z.
 - All the above are conceptual questions asked by experienced researchers.

³ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 223.

⁴ Turabian, 16.

5. **Which type of notes are preferred for referencing in a thesis or dissertation, because they are easier to read?**

- Endnotes.
- Numbering notes.
- Formatting notes.
- Footnotes.⁵**

6. **In qualitative research, planning the analysis of your findings can be done in the following ways,**

- Quantify your data by coding, synthesize your data.
- Seeking patterns of your data, describe and interpret data, synthesize your data.⁶**
- Sort and categorize your data, synthesize your data.
- Review and explore the data, synthesize your data.

7. **Formulating a research committee is important for the defense of your dissertation. The purpose of the dissertation defense is to?**

- Publicly discuss your research and evaluate the acceptability of your study.⁷**
- Properly file and store your dissertation with multiple researchers.
- Submit hard copy of your dissertation in case you lose the soft copy.

⁵ Turabian, 95.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 129.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 172.

- Seek approval of your dissertation before it is published.
8. **How should dates be formally written according to the European Commission style guide?**
- Write out the day, preceded by the month separated by a hard space.
- Write out the day, month, and all the last two digits of the year.
- Write out the month, preceded by a simple figure for the day, separated by a hard space.⁸**
- Write out the day, preceded by the month and all the four digits of the year.
9. **When is it necessary to use italics when writing in English text?**
- When writing foreign words and phrases.⁹**
- When writing words and phrases that emphasize your claims.
- When writing hyphenated words.
- When writing direct speech and verbatim quotes.
10. **According to the European Commission style guide, how should the list of European Union member states be listed?**
- The countries should be listed in alphabetical order in both in English and legislation.
- The countries should be listed in protocol order in both in English and legislation.

⁸ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission. 7th Edition* (Brussels: Directorate-General for Translation, 2011), 25.

⁹ European Commission, 31.

- The countries should be listed in protocol order in English and in alphabetical order in legislation.
- The countries should be listed in alphabetical order in English and in protocol order in legislation.**¹⁰

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Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008.

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¹⁰ European Commission, 72.